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First Develop India and Make in India: The New Face of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

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1. INTRODUCTION

The last two decades of the 20th century witnessed a dramatic world-wide increase in foreign direct investment (FDI), accompanied by a marked change in the attitude of most developing countries towards inward FDI. As against a highly suspicious attitude of these countries towards inward FDI in the past, most countries now regard FDI as beneficial for their development efforts and compete with each other to attract it. The explanation for this in attitude lies in the changes in political and economic systems that have occurred during the closing years of the last century. Many countries, particularly in Eastern Europe, have abandoned socialism in its various forms and have embraced the market economy. In many of these countries, mass privatization has taken place mainly with funds from abroad. The success of Southeast and East Asian economies is attributable, to a large extent, to a high level of foreign investment and export promotion.

Countries of the world, particularly developing economies, are vying with each other to attract foreign capital to boost their domestic rates of investment and also to acquire new technology and managerial skills.

Intense competition is taking place among the fund-starved less developed countries to lure foreign investors by offering repatriation facilities, tax concessions and other incentives. However, FDI is not an unmixed blessing. Governments in developing countries have to be very careful while deciding the magnitude, pattern and conditions of private foreign investment.

The growth of FDI flows to developing countries is unevenly distributed among regions and groups of developing countries. Most FDI flows continue still to be concentrated in 10 to 15 host countries overwhelmingly in Asia and Latin America. South, East and Southeast Asia has experienced the fastest economic growth in the World, and emerged as the largest host region. China is now the largest host country in the developing world.

Figure 1
FDI Inflows, Global and by Group of Economies, 1995-2013 and Projections, 2014-2016 (Billions of dollars)

Source: UNCTAD FDI-TNC-GVC Information System, FDI/TNC database (www.unctad.org/fdistatistics)

Table 1: Sectors Attracting Highest FDI Inflows in India

(During August 1991 to March 2006)

Sector	Amount of FDI Inflows	
	Rs. Crore	US\$ Million
1. Electrical Equipment	23709	5496
2. Telecommunication	14337	3372
3. Transport Industry	13315	3178
4. Energy	10976	2581
5. Service Sector	12804	3091
6. Chemicals	8580	2143
7. Hotel and Tourism	4984	1371
8. Food Processing Industries	4702	1179
9. Metallurgical Industries	2816	655
10. Textiles	1775	450

Source: Government of India, Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Foreign Direct Investment Policy, April 2006.

Report of the Committee on FDI, 2002:

Committee on Foreign Direct Investment (Chairman: N. K. Singh), which submitted its report in September 2002 to the Prime Minister, has recommended that the ban on FDI in retail trade should not be lifted. In other sectors including oil marketing, petroleum exploration, banking and financial services and real estate, the Committee suggested rising of FDI limit to 100 per cent.

The Committee proposed a desegregation of the FDI target for the Tenth Plan in terms of sector and relevant administrative ministers and departments to increase accountability and expedite decision making.

For speeding up project implementation, the Committee observed that the Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB) should be empowered to give initial central level registrations and approvals wherever possible. The government rules of business should be changed to empower the Foreign Investment

Implementation Authority (FIIA) to expedite the processing of administrative and policy approvals if adopted.

2. PRIME MINISTER NARENDRA MODI AND FDI

Consistency and stability in government policies is important to build trust between the industry and the government. Integral to developing and maintaining this trust is redefining the way Centre and State governments work by bringing good governance principals to the fore. To realize this vision, the government and its several constituent arms have put into motion several for reaching changes that have a bearing on improving the manufacturing ecosystem in the country.

Ease of doing business, focus on Public Private Partnerships, harnessing the potential of Democracy, Demography and Demand—that's what forms the key focus of *Prime Minister Narendra Modi's 'Make in India' Campaign*. "Development of States is important. States and Centre have to work together to attract investment. Development of States is development of India. We are aggressively going to work towards export promotion. We have to change the economic dynamics; we have to improve manufacturing in a fashion that benefits the poor. This is a cycle, move poor people towards being a part of middle class. Manufacturing boost will create jobs, increase purchasing power, thereby creating a larger market for manufacturers. We need to enhance the purchasing power of Indians. For Indians FDI is a responsibility, it means to FIRST DEVELOP INDIA, for global investors FDI is an opportunity in the form of Foreign Direct Investment."

PM Narendra Modi first made the pitch for 'Make in India' during his maiden Independence Day speech from the ramparts of Red Fort "If we have to put in use the education, the capability of the youth, we will have to go for manufacturing sector and for this Hindustan also will have to lend its full

strength, but we also invite world powers. Therefore I want to appeal the entire people world over, from the ramparts of the Red Fort, "Come, make in India", "Come, manufacture in India". Sell in any country of the world but manufacture here. We have got skill, talent, discipline, and determination to do something. We want to give the world an favourable opportunity that come here, "Come, Make in India" and we will say to the world, from electrical to electronics, "Come, Make in India", from automobiles to agro value addition "Come, Make in India", paper or plastic, "Come, Make in India", satellite or submarine "Come, Make in India". Our country is powerful. Come, I am giving you an invitation. Brothers and sisters, I want to call upon the youth of the country, particularly the small people engaged in the industrial sector. I want to call upon the youth working in the field of technical education in the country. As I say to the world "Come, Make in India", I say to the youth of the country - it should be our dream that this message reaches every corner of the world, "Made in India". This should be our dream.

This is a path-breaking venture. In fact, the vision statement of official website, www.makeinindia.gov.in commits to achieve for the country among other things an increase in manufacturing sector growth to 12-14 % per annum over the medium term, increase in the share of manufacturing in the country's Gross Domestic Product from 16% to 25% by 2022 and importantly to create 100 million additional jobs by 2022 in the manufacturing sector alone. These are quite highly ambitious targets given the background that the manufacturing sector in India, which accounts for fourth-fifth of the total output, grew a meager 3.3 per cent in January 2010.

Achievable Targets:

Target of an increase in manufacturing sector growth to 12-14% per annum over the medium term.

An increase in the share of manufacturing in the country's Gross Domestic Product from 16% to 25% by 2022.

To create 100 million additional jobs by 2022 in manufacturing sector.

Creation of appropriate skill sets among rural migrants and the urban poor for inclusive growth.

Tapping Golden Opportunity:

The initiative can actually benefit India from the ground reality, especially when the Chinese manufacturing leaps have come under strain. There are already reports that several western manufacturing players operating in China want to move away from the world's largest manufacturing hub. Analysts say, Chinese wages are going up and the labour market is getting more challenging and that is driving away investors. Thus companies with operating factories in China should look for other alternatives in the region, such as Vietnam, Indonesia and of course India.

The country is expected to rank amongst the world's top three growth economies and amongst the top three manufacturing destinations by as early as 2020. This is far more ambitious scene than promised about 2050 sometime back in the context of India's role at the BRICS level. Indian manufacturing sector has positive elements like "favourable demographic dividends" for the next 2-3 decades. The sustained availability of quality workforce is another advantage.

Importantly again, in India, the cost of manpower is relatively low as compared to other countries. There are responsible business houses operating with credibility and professionalism. The country has a democratized polity *vis-a-vis* the rule of law and a strong consumerism intake ability of the domestic market.

Favourable Milestones:

India has already marked its presence as one of the fastest growing economies of the world.

The country is expected to rank amongst the world's top three growth economies and amongst the top three manufacturing destinations by 2020.

Favourable demographic dividends for the next 2-3 decades. Sustained availability of quality workforce.

The cost of manpower is relatively low as compared to other countries.

The government has also pledged other focused approaches. Among other things, it intends to leverage the existing incentives/schemes to boost manufacturing. A technology acquisition and development fund has been proposed for the acquisition of appropriate technologies, the creation of a patent pool and the development of domestic manufacturing of equipment used for controlling pollution and reducing energy consumption, official sources said in New Delhi.

Training of Workforce:

The manufacturing sector cannot develop on its own without skilled labour force and in this context it is heartening to note the government's initiatives for skill development. The creation of appropriate skill would definitely set rural migrants and the urban poor on a track towards inclusive growth. That would be a vital step for boosting manufacturing.

The New Ministry for Skill Development and Entrepreneurship has initiated the process of revising the National Policy on Skill Development. It is significant to note that under the Rural Development ministry, the Modi government has undertaken another new initiative for skill development under a recast programme named after BJP icon Pt. Deendayal Upadhyaya. The new training programme envisages setting up of at least 1500 to 2000 training centres across the coun-

try and the entire project would result in an estimated expenditure of Rs 2000 crore and will be run on PPP model. The new training programme would enable the youths to get jobs in demand-oriented markets like Spain, US, Japan, Russia, France, China, UK and West Asia. The government proposes to train about 3 lakh youths annually in first two years and by the end of 2017, it has set a target of reaching out to as many as 10 lakh rural youths.

3. CAUSES AND REASONS FOR LOW FDI IN RECENT INDIA

Some factors may be more relevant for first time investors with no previous experience of investment in India. The review presents broad generalizations basing on past experiences.

a) **Attitudinal Assessment:** Although, economic reforms introduced in nineties have paved the path to foreign capital but, some unhappy episodes in the past have given multiple effects adversely to the business environment in India. There has been a perception abroad that foreign investors are looked at with some suspicion even today in India. When a foreign investor considers making any new investment decision, it goes through four stages in the decision making process and action cycle, namely, (a) screening, (b) planning, (c) implementing and (d) operating and expanding. Often India is dropped out at the screening stage itself. This is primarily because our promotional attitude is quite often of a general nature and not corporate specific. India is, moreover, a multi-cultural society and a large number of multi-national companies (MNC) do not understand the diversity and the multi-plural nature of the society and the different stakeholders in this country.

All investments, foreign and domestic are made under the expectation of future profits. The economy benefits if economic policy fosters competition, creates a well functioning modern regulatory system and discourages

artificial monopolies created by the government through entry barriers. A recognition and understanding of these facts can result in a more positive attitude towards FDI.

b) Policy Frameworks: Most of the problems for investors arise because of domestic policy, rules and procedures and not the FDI policy per se or its rules and procedures. The FDI policy, which has a lot of positive features, is discussed, before highlighting the domestic policy related difficulties that are commonly the focus of adverse comment by investors and intermediaries.

c) Quality of Infrastructure: Poor infrastructure affects the productivity of the economy as a whole and particular to GDP/per capita GDP. It also reduces the comparative advantage of industries that are more intensive in the use of such infrastructure. In the context of FDI, poor infrastructure has a greater effect on export production than on production for the domestic market. FDI directed at the domestic market suffers the same handicap and additional costs as domestic manufacturers that are competing for the domestic market. Inadequate and poor quality roads, railways and ports, however raise export costs vis-à-vis global competitors having better quality and lower cost infrastructure. These costs have been quantified by the CII- World Bank study of Investment environment in India and its comparison with similar World Bank studied on China and other countries. As a foreign direct investor planning to set up an export base in developing/ emerging economies has the option of choosing between India and other locations with better infrastructure, India is handicapped in attracting export oriented FDI.

Poor infrastructure is found to be the most important constraint for construction and engineering industries. It is also evident by the survey made by Mckinsey, "Law, rules, regulations relating to infrastructure are some-

times missing or unclear e.g. LNG and the power sector are beset with multiple problems such as State monopoly, bankruptcy and weak regulators".

4. BENEFITS OF PM NARENDRA MODI'S VISION OF FDI

Benefits include moving away from an industry focus on intermediaries and job creation.

a) Infusion of Capital: As discussed above, retailing depends on supply chain logistics. An efficient logistics - based on well-developed networks of transportation, communication, and storage infrastructure – not only provides timely and uninterrupted market access to the producers but also ensures quality and lower prices to the consumers. For example, without the development of appropriate storage infrastructure, the farmers cannot have an access to an efficient market system that pays fair prices and have to fall prey to unscrupulous middlemen. These middlemen pay lower prices to the farmers and charge higher prices to the retailers. Furthermore, since a significant portion of the produces are destroyed in the process of being transported from the farmers to the retailers and ultimately to the consumers, the consumers have to pay higher prices for relatively low quality products. In India, primarily due to the unorganised and fragmented nature of the retail sector, there is a severe shortage of funds for investment in the basic infrastructure required mainly for back-end retail logistics. The retailers are too small to make such large investments. Although government has stepped in, the infrastructure built by the government has not been adequate. Allowing FDI in retailing is expected to go a long way in alleviating this situation because the large retailers would build the necessary infrastructure to create an integrated back-end supply chain for efficiency.

b) Technology Transfer: In addition to augmenting physical capital stock, FDI in de-

veloping countries also acts as a conduit of technology transfer. Foreign capital brings along advanced technology from developed countries that increases productivity. In retailing, advanced technologies will tremendously improve processing, grading, handling and packaging of goods. The use of cold-storage facilities, refrigerated vans, pre-cooling chambers will reduce wastage and help maintain product quality. Electronic weighing, billing, and barcode scanning will add to accuracy and efficiency. These efficiency gains will lower price and improve quality for the consumers.

c) Moving away from intermediary-only benefits: Today's intermediaries amid producers and customers add no value to the products, adding hugely to final costs instead. By the time products filter through various intermediaries and into the marketplace, they lose freshness and quality, and often go to waste. However, intermediaries garner huge profits by distributing these losses between producers and customers by buying products at low prices from producers, but selling at extremely marked-up prices to consumers. In an unbalanced system that incorporates multiple intermediaries simply for logistics, only intermediaries benefit. With organized retail, every intermediate step – procurement, processing, transport and delivery – adds value to the product. This happens because it uses international best practices and modern technology, ensuring maximum efficiency and minimum waste. Organized retail enables on-site processing, scientific handling and quick transport through cold storage chains to the final consumer.

d) Job Creation: Despite predictions from some analysts that millions of jobs would be lost due to FDI in retail, it may in fact be the other way around. With the entry of branded retailers, the market will increase, creating additional employment in retail and other tertiary sectors. Given their professional ap-

proach, organized retailers will allot some quantity of resources towards the training and development of the resources they employ.

5. CONCLUSION

Export is picking up giving a slight push to the economy. Experts also believe that the current account deficit is likely to decrease this fiscal year. Modi believes in "modernisation without Westernisation". Though we are seeing some improvements in certain sectors, time only will tell if Modi can change India or not, whether he can make India a better place to live in. With an eye on wooing US investors during his much-hyped tour, Modi added the term 'Link West' to the expression of 'Look East' (policy) and said a global vision was essential for the 'Make in India' initiative to succeed. Admitting that it was not possible to attract investment by an invitation or through incentives, he said, "The biggest issue is trust. The government will intervene only if it sees any deficiencies. We do not want any industrialist being forced to leave India." He said the biggest initiative his government has undertaken is allowing businesses to do self-certification, thereby placing trust in businesspersons. Among the new initiatives are Digital India Mission for information highways, wealth from waste mission to recycle waste, gas and water grids that would complement nationwide electricity grid and an expansive optical fibre network.

If effectively implemented, such FDI has the potential to:

- It may bring not only foreign capital but also technology and expertise.
- It may help to build an efficient linkage between the back – end supply chain and the front – end via capital investment and technological inputs.
- It can develop a better farmer to consumer network through better expertise and control and bulk purchases from the farmers.

- d. It may ensure efficient and effective transportation by reducing transit costs and other relative costs.
- e. Foreign companies have better managerial capacities in minimizing the wastage through effective cold storage, transport infrastructure, warehousing, treatment, processing and perishing.
- f. It may help farmers (the client) in providing them consultancy about increasing productive and preserving the harvest.

Thus, Political influence must leave their old outlook as overpowered by the Imperialism and government should foresee the future and rising demands of the country. Modern youth needs a respectable and comfortable job, quality education, rural areas need upbringing and urban areas need industrialization.

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